

Analyzing the Effects of Aerosol Release on Solar Albedo Through Natural and Artificial Processes

By Vihaan Sawardekar

Abstract:

Albedo modification, a novel technique, involves modifying the reflection of solar radiation to help mitigate climate change impacts. Albedo is defined as the reflectivity of a surface and this property influences the energy balance of the Earth by controlling the amount of light absorbed or reflected. Aerosols, both natural and artificial, impact the albedo of the atmosphere in a process known as albedo modification. Natural modification occurs during large-scale events such as volcanoes, dust storms, wildfires and more. Volcanic degassing significantly impacts cloud albedo by releasing sulfur. On the other hand, wildfires have been linked to reducing glacier albedo and rising sea levels. Synthetic aerosol injection, such as the release of synthetic aerosols, has been proposed as a method to stop global warming. These methods have raised ethical concerns due to correlation with poor atmospheric air quality.

Introduction:

Albedo modification represents a groundbreaking aspect of modern geoengineering. Albedo, as defined as the reflectivity of a surface, plays a key role in countering the devastating effect of problems like global warming, climate change, heat deserts, and more. The intentional manipulation of albedo through the introduction of aerosols can change the reflectivity of the earth's atmosphere, and thus change the amount of light absorbed or released. Although the research has potential, it can modify other factors of an environment. Aerosols, which are fine particles in the atmosphere, can come from both natural sources as well as artificial and industrial ones. Volcanic eruptions, wildfires, and dust storms are some of the natural catastrophic events that can modify climates through the release of aerosol. The interaction between aerosols and the earth's atmosphere plays a pivotal role in the Earth's energy balance. The ability of aerosols to alter solar albedo leads to both opportunities and challenges. It provides a

means of temporarily cooling the planet, but leads to unintentional side effects, and ethical concerns.

Research:

The two main parts of albedo modification are aerosols through natural processes and aerosols through artificial processes. The release of aerosols through natural processes are majorly uncontrollable events that alter the climate. Albedo modification is majorly through the change of reflectivity of the atmosphere due to aerosols. Aerosols majorly lie in the stratosphere after injection.

One major natural process that can cause albedo modification through the release of aerosols in volcanic eruptions. Volcanoes, in a process known as volcanic degassing, actively omit gasses such as sulfur, even without major explosive eruptions(Andronova et al., 1999). Volcanic degassing increased cloud droplets by 40% in pre-industrial times(Schmidt et al., 2012). This is conflicted with a significantly lower 10% increase during industrial times/present day(Schmidt et al., 2012). The cloud albedo effect refers to how much sunlight the clouds reflect. During the pre-industrial era the cloud albedo caused by degassing was -1.06 W/m^2 , whereas the present day was -0.56 W/m^2 (Schmidt et al., 2012). The pre-industrial cloud albedo was stronger, meaning it reflected more light. The reason for the difference was that the background aerosol level during the pre-industrial era was lower, causing the degassing increase to be more prominent and cause a higher change. Present-day aerosol levels are much higher, meaning the change is less pronounced.

The next major, natural cause of aerosol in the stratosphere is wildfires. Here we will specifically explore the effect of this type of aerosol on the place it has the biggest effect: glaciers. Following extensive wildfires in 2015, the glacier's albedo decreased from 0.29 in 2015 to 0.16 in 2018 and remained low in the following years(Aubry-Wake et al., 2022). The reduction in albedo was substantial and affected the glaciers for a long period of time yet to come. In fact, the reduction in albedo led to an increase in the glacier's melt by over 10% (Aubry-Wake et al., 2022). This contributed to an 0.42m water increase in 2019 and 0.37m in 2020(Aubry-Wake et al., 2022). These changes resulted in an average net radiation decrease of 15 W/m^2 (Aubry-Wake et al., 2022).

Over the past decade, glaciers across the world have been impacted because of changing albedo. Out of 17 regions studied using MODIS data, 15 showed a decline in albedo(Williamson & Menounos, 2021). The steady decline was furthered due to a substantial correlation between temperatures and albedo along with a correlation between albedo and aerosols(Williamson & Menounos, 2021). Forest fires have been correlated with changing numbers of light absorbing aerosols in the atmosphere, and thus affecting the melt-rate of glaciers.

Synthetic aerosol modification can also be used to mitigate the effects of global warming. The release of sulfate particles, an aerosol, can be used to counteract warming by increasing cloud albedo. The increase in cloud albedo means reflecting more solar radiation back into space(Crutzen, n.d.). However, these same sulfate particles cause over 500,000 deaths and ecological damage(Crutzen, n.d.). Declining sulfur dioxide emissions at precisely 2.7% a year has been correlated with increased global warming through lower reflection of solar radiation. This brings up an ethical concern of priority between atmospheric air quality and atmospheric albedo.

High albedo materials provide a viable, high impact solution to tackling global warming. Although they have drawbacks, they are predicted to have a much larger and easier impact than simply reducing CO₂ emissions(Cotana et al., 2014). Scientists have tested a method of synthetic albedo by adding hollow glass microspheres(Johnson et al., 2022). This method increased surface albedo from 0.17 to 0.36. This increase led to a 33% decrease in the ice melting rate(Johnson et al., 2022).

Conclusion:

Overall, natural albedo has made a substantial impact on our community in the past due to climatic events such as volcanic eruptions and degassing, dust storms, wildfires, and more. These events are unchangeable and impact our climate by causing aerosols to enter the Earth's atmosphere. These aerosols then change the solar albedo causing more light to either be absorbed or reflected. This reaction can be harnessed to synthetically manufacture the composition of the atmosphere and create beneficial effects to counteract climate change.

Works Cited(APA 7th)

- Andronova, N. G., Rozanov, E. V., Yang, F., Schlesinger, M. E., & Stenchikov, G. L. (1999). Radiative forcing by volcanic aerosols from 1850 to 1994. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, *104*(D14), 16807–16826.
<https://doi.org/10.1029/1999jd900165>
- Aubry-Wake, C., Bertoincini, A., & Pomeroy, J. W. (2022). Fire and Ice: The Impact of Wildfire-Affected Albedo and Irradiance on Glacier Melt. *Earth's Future*, *10*(4).
<https://doi.org/10.1029/2022ef002685>
- Cotana, F., Rossi, F., Filipponi, M., Coccia, V., Pisello, A. L., Bonamente, E., Petrozzi, A., & Cavalaglio, G. (2014). Albedo control as an effective strategy to tackle Global Warming: A case study. *Applied Energy*, *130*, 641–647.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.02.065>
- Crutzen, P. (n.d.). *Albedo Enhancement by Stratospheric Sulfur Injections: A Contribution to Resolve a Policy Dilemma? - ProQuest*. www.proquest.com.
<https://www.proquest.com/openview/9foa629d28adfa02e164457e63fb7e6b/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=36297>
- Irvine, P. J., Ridgwell, A., & Lunt, D. J. (2011). Climatic effects of surface albedo geoengineering. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, *116*(D24), n/a-n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011jd016281>
- Johnson, D., Manzara, A., Field, L. A., Chamberlin, D. R., & Sholtz, A. (2022). A Controlled Experiment of Surface Albedo Modification to Reduce Ice Melt. *Earth's Future*, *10*(12). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022ef002883>

Schmidt, A., Carslaw, K. S., Mann, G. W., Rap, A., Pringle, K. J., Spracklen, D. V.,

Wilson, M., & Forster, P. M. (2012). Importance of tropospheric volcanic aerosol for indirect radiative forcing of climate. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, *12*(16), 7321–7339. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-12-7321-2012>

Williamson, S. N., & Menounos, B. (2021). The influence of forest fires aerosol and air temperature on glacier albedo, western North America. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, *267*, 112732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2021.112732>